

Develop and deliver a Science Gateway or an HPC portal on OneSciencePlace

Duration: 90 mins

Recommended skill: Beginner

Requirements: Web browser

Project website: OneSciencePlace.org

OneSciencePlace® is a modern, extensible, and fully managed and composable platform to create an HPC portal, a science gateway, a data sharing hub, or a publication repository through an intuitive, low-code/no-code environment. Designed to serve the full spectrum of the research ecosystem, OneSciencePlace empowers principal investigators, educators, research teams, HPC administrators, and institutional stakeholders alike. Whether supporting a single user, a classroom, a collaborative research group, or a campus-wide initiative, the platform scales effortlessly to meet diverse needs.

At its core, everything on OneSciencePlace is content, including applications, data, publications, and tools, making it easy to curate, present, and extend scientific resources. With built-in FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and seamless integration across computational and storage backends (on-premises or cloud), OneSciencePlace transforms how cyberinfrastructure is delivered at a fraction of the cost and with minimal administrative burden.

The OneSciencePlace platform is built on a set of mature technologies, including Drupal, SeedMeLab, Tapis, and others. It can seamlessly interface with multiple compute resources, including Linux hosts, HPC clusters, and storage resources such as POSIX file systems or S3 object storage.

The tutorial builds upon the success from last year and will include the latest developments of the system. This tutorial will focus on Science Gateway and HPC portal use cases, guiding attendees to explore OneSciencePlace in a hands-on manner. An outline of the tutorial agenda is provided below, which will include presentation, review, and hands-on components.

Agenda

- Tutorial account logistics (5 mins)
- Overview of OneSciencePlace Platform (20 mins)
- Apps: Running applications (Hands-on) (10 mins)
 - Interactive Web app (containerized): Jupyter & RStudio
 - Interactive VNC app (containerized): Linux Desktop
 - Batch command line app: Executable on an Elastic Slurm cluster on AWS
- Compute systems available for tutorial (Review) (10 mins)
- Complex apps and their UI (Review) (10 mins)
- Creating a simple app and its custom UI (Hands-on) (15 mins)
- Add new compute system (Review) (10 mins)
- Publishing on the gateway (Review) (10 mins)
- Discussion

Attendee outcomes

The tutorial will enable attendees to gain hands-on experience with the OneSciencePlace platform and ...

- Learn to use apps on two systems: A linux host and an HPC cluster
- Learn to create a new app along with its user interface with no-code

- Gain an understanding of the feasibility of enabling and empowering users to bring their applications.
- Germinate ideas to compose a single user-facing environment that seamlessly integrates multiple clusters/hosts within and across institutions.